

Nature Engagement and Care: Concepts for Cultivating Inclusive Outdoor Participation and Responsible Outdoor Access

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Background

An established body of research supports the role of outdoor natural environments in relation to health and wellbeing and increasing visits to the outdoors has been one of the Scottish Government's [National Performance Framework](#) indicators¹ since 2006. Current trends suggest that more people are visiting the outdoors more regularly ([Scottish Government, 2024²](#)). Use of the outdoors, however, varies between population sub-groups (e.g. age, gender) and there is ongoing interest in how to encourage engagement with nature more widely. Yet, more people, from more population groups, doing more outdoor activity, more often, has the potential for negative impact – for the natural landscape, for domesticated and wild species, and for benefits derived.

This research summary provides an overview of two concepts being developed within the Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing (JHI-C6-1) project to inform strategies to foster both inclusive *and* sustainable engagement with the outdoors. These concepts draw on existing data (collected via previous Scottish Government Strategic Research Programmes) and debates within the literature.

Nature Engagement

The nature engagement concept focuses on how we might get more people outside. It draws on an integrative public health 'behaviour change wheel'³ developed to facilitate designing, evaluating, and characterising behaviour change interventions. The behaviour change model works on the basis that *behaviour* (B) results from an interaction of *capability* (C), *opportunity* (O), and *motivation* (M) – the COM-B system. Figure 1 illustrates this interaction and details the subdivisions within each component which reflect important distinctions noted in behaviour change research literature.

Figure 1 The COM-B system (modified from Michie et al. (2011); reproduced under open license CC by 2.0).

¹ <https://nationalperformance.gov.scot/national-outcomes>

² <https://nationalperformance.gov.scot/national-outcomes/explore-national-outcomes/environment/measuring-progress-environment#Visits-to-the-outdoors>

³ Michie, S.; Van Stralen, M.M.; West, R. (2011). The behaviour change wheel: a new method for characterising and designing behaviour change interventions. *Implementation Sci.* 6, 1-12.

A recent evaluation of a nature-based intervention to promote physical activity – a group outdoor health walk – identified capabilities, opportunities, and motivations relevant not only to the target behaviour but also to engagement with nature outwith the walk programme (Irvine et al., 2024). Box 1 provides specific examples of these in relation to people spending time outdoors.

Box 1: Nature Engagement (drawn from Irvine et al., 2024)		
COM-B model component	Component subsets	Examples
Capabilities	Physical capability	Physical strength and stamina
	Psychological capability	Knowledge of weather or terrain types, and how to navigate them
Opportunities	Physical opportunities	Infrastructure, such as pathways
	Social opportunity	Accessibility of peer support groups
Motivations	Reflective motivation	Intentional interest in exploring the outdoor space
	Automatic motivation	Pleasant feelings evoked from spending time in the outdoor space

In addition to physical and social opportunities external to the person which can support (or not) nature engagement, there are important person-specific capabilities and motivations that nature-based interventions can foster. For example, one aspect of people-environment interaction is the availability of a ‘mental map’ (i.e. internal representation) of an external environment which can guide people’s perceptions, decisions, and behaviour.^{4,5}

Here we see that taking part in a structured group outdoor walk to promote physical health can support the expansion of one’s mental map about the outdoors – its paths, terrain, weather. Moving from a focus on barriers to framing engagement in terms of capabilities is useful in that it: (i) helps us think in a different way about why people do or do not engage; and (ii) places focus on the ways in which nature-based interventions can help enable and empower people to more fully engage with Scotland’s landscapes and natural environments.

Care for Nature

The care for nature concept focuses on responsible outdoor behaviour. It specifically considers the idea of care. This notion is explicitly present in the Scottish Outdoor Access Code (Box 1) and implicitly conveyed in the other two principles underpinning SOAC (Respecting the interests of others, and Taking responsibility for your own actions), as well as in narratives of ‘careless’ recreational users or behaviours.

⁴ Kaplan S.; Kaplan, R. (1989). *Cognition and environment: Functioning in an uncertain world*. Ulrich’s: Ann Arbor, MI, USA. (Original work published 1982).

⁵ Kitchin, R. (1994). Cognitive maps: what are they and why study them? *J. Environ Psychol.* 14(1):1–19.

Box 1: The idea of 'care' within the Scottish Outdoor Access Code

In the Scottish Outdoor Access Code (2005, Section 1.3) one of the three key principles underpinning the right of responsible access is "Care for the environment. If you are exercising access rights, look after the places you visit and enjoy, and leave the land as you find it. If you are a land manager, help maintain the natural and cultural features which make the outdoors attractive to visit and enjoy" (Section 1.3).

Here we consider care as:

... everything that is done to maintain, continue, and repair "the world" so that all ... can live in it as well as possible ... [including] all that we seek to interweave in a complex, life-sustaining web.^{6,7}

Within the care concept there are three interrelated dimensions. The first is the *practice of care*, which is something we can do. The second is the *feelings of care*, which is something we can feel. The third is the *ethics of care*, which is something we can know and commit to. Box 2 illustrates these dimensions in relation to our qualitative exploration of recreational disturbances of wildlife. The case study considers dogwalker taking outdoor access in a forest where the recreational disturbance of wildlife has been identified as a particular risk to endangered species.

Box 2: Dimensions of care

Dimension of care	Example
The practice of care	The labour of care – i.e., putting a dog on a lead
The feelings of care	Care experienced through bodily affect e.g. the discomfort of having a dog on a lead, love of wildlife
The ethics of care	Moral imperatives to look after something or someone – i.e., commitment to protecting the environment.

The practice of care is often considered to be the most important dimension. Indeed, undertaking care of one thing, for example walking a dog, may come at the cost of something else – for example a now disturbed ecosystem. Our case study findings highlight the complexity of care in the context of outdoor access. It may relate not only to care for the environment by the recreational user but also care for pets, children, other family members, work obligations, or the care for self. It also includes the duty of care a land manager has regarding managing outdoor access.

Our care concept additionally emphasises the importance of understanding how feelings and ethics of care can influence the practice of care. Capacities to care include available emotional, physical, and attentional skills during different times (of day, of year, of life stage) and in different spaces (habitats, frame of mind). These capacities are shaped by cultural assumptions (relating for example to gender, class, age) and what the physical and social environments enable.

Thinking about who is able to care at any given time, what or who requires care, what might facilitate increased care of the outdoors and those who use it may help with the design of more effective policy interventions. In this way, capacities of care may be increased, thereby increasing responsible behaviours (Brown, Lackova & Banks, in prep.).

⁶ Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017, p.161, after Tronto 1993, p. 103; Puig de la Bellacasa, M. (2017). *Matters of Care: Speculative Ethics in More Than Human Worlds*. London: University of Minnesota Press.

⁷ Tronto, J.C. 1993. *Moral Boundaries - A Political Argument for an Ethic of Care*, London, UK, Routledge.

Next Steps

Recreational use forms an integral part of land management decisions, while how people engage with the outdoors has environmental implications. Policy makers, practitioners, and scholars are increasingly recognising the need to cultivate conditions for a reciprocal relationship between people and the environment, one that nurtures the human community and integrates care for, and responsible access to, nature by people.

We will continue to develop the two concepts in three ways. First, we complete our analysis of the Scottish Outdoor Access Code using the concepts as a lens through which to understand engagement and care. Second, we will extend our fieldwork utilising virtual tours of nature to specifically explore engagement capabilities and responsible behaviour with different population sub-groups. Third, we will look at ways to integrate the concepts, for example, through the notion of capabilities and capacities.

Box 3 provides examples of the two concepts working alongside one another. In this way we will further our understanding of ways to cultivate nature engagement and care.

Box 3: Example of integration of the nature engagement and care concepts

Consider the example of a person on a walk in the outdoors near capercaillie habitat, walking with their dog whilst pushing their baby in a buggy. They know where to go, and where they can go whilst walking with the dog (so they have *psychological capabilities*, as explained by the nature engagement concept), but their current *capacity to care* (as considered in the care concept) is qualified by having the baby with them, both due to the increased caring responsibilities this presents and the limited access of the buggy.

Imagine that in this scenario the dog the person is walking with starts to behave badly, whilst they know that an individual who knows them personally is not far behind them on the walk. Ordinarily they may stop and get the dog under control, but given reduced *capacity to care* in their current situation, and the increased *social pressure* they choose to continue on. In this case, social pressure – which can act as an external support for nature engagement, has acted as a *social norm* that has impacted how someone behaves.

Acknowledgements: This work was funded by the Scottish Government's Rural and Environmental Science & Analytical Services (RESAS) Strategic Research Programme 2022-2027 (Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing [JHI-C6-1]). This summary corresponds to Deliverable D5.1 submitted as part of work package titled 'Nature engagement capabilities' (WP3).

Suggested citation: Irvine, K.N., Brown, K., & Thompson, C. (2024). *Nature Engagement and Care: Concepts for Cultivating Inclusive Outdoor Participation and Responsible Outdoor Access*. Deliverable D5 for Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing (JHI-C6-1), The James Hutton Institute, Aberdeen, Scotland. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17558735

Further information:

Brown, K.M.; Lackova, P.; Banks, E. (in prep.) 'Taking care' in recreation and conservation: How configurations of care matter in managing wildlife disturbance from outdoor access.

Irvine, K.N.; Fisher, D.; Currie, M.; Colley, K.; Warber, S.L. (2024). Using the COM-B model to examine user experience of a nature-based intervention to promote physical activity in older adults with chronic health conditions: a qualitative study. *International Journal for Environmental Research and Public Health*, 21(7): 843.

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